

EMILE DURKHEIM'S THEORY ON SUICIDE AND ITS APPLICATION IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Suicide is a global public health problem and Nigeria is one of the epicentres of suicide in the world. It has threatened the existence of mankind and affects the Nigerian society adversely hence it becomes very necessary to subject the suicide incidence in Nigeria to a scientific research as well as proffer solution to incidence of suicide in Nigeria. The paper assessed the high rate of suicide in Nigeria using the Emile Durkhiem work on suicide. It also reviewed some empirical literature, theoretical literature, relevant theories and presented a theoretical framework for the study. For its methodology and materials, this study adopts a qualitative research design, focusing on the interpretative analysis of social phenomena through the lens of Emile Durkheim's theory, particularly his concepts of social facts, collective conscience and anomie as they apply to Nigerian society. 20 respondents were interview through purposive sampling. These included five university sociology lecturers, five religious leaders (Christian and Muslim), five community leaders (Urban and rural), five youth representatives. the paper also searched, collected and analyzed published news reports about suicide form newspapers in Nigeria. A total of three hundred and fifty (350) suicide reports were assessed between Jan 2015 and December 2023. In its findings, it was highlighted that Nigeria suicide rate is 17.3 per 100,000 which is higher than the global 10.5 per 100,000 and that issues like financial constraints occasioned by the current economic hardship, marital conflicts and mental illness can cause suicide. The paper therefore recommends that government should reduce inflation rate and properly implement palliative measures so as to reduce suffering of the masses. Also, people should engage in family re-orientation, seek medical help after trauma and live a stress-free life, as these measures will drastically reduce the suicide rate in the country.

Keywords – Suicide, suicide rate, economic hardship, marital conflict, stress, trauma and family re-orientation.

INTRODUCTION

Suicide is “the action of killing oneself intentionally, Black’s Law Dictionary defines suicide as the willful and voluntary act of a person who understands the physical nature of the act, and intends by it to accomplish the result of self-destruction”. “The deliberate termination of one’s existence while in the possession and enjoyment of his mental faculties. This means that the person committing suicide is in his right mind and did it voluntarily.

There was the case of Dr. Allwell Orji, a medical doctor. He had instructed his driver to park the car on the bridge. He then jumped into the Lagoon. His body was found a few days later. Another incidence involved in 51 years old lady who highly indebted tried to commit suicide but was rescued. (Punch, Aug 17, 2017).

Nigeria has one of the highlight suicide rates in Africa. No fewer than seventy-nine persons have committed suicide in Nigeria in 2022. According to Ma Manah (2023), suicide is the fourth longest cause of death in the world.

Findings from Nigerian Punch (Aug 12 2022), showed that 79 persons comprising 70 males and 9 females committed suicide during this period.

Lagos ranked highest with 12 suicide cases, followed by Oyo 10, Kano four, Anambra three, Edo three, Delta three, Ogun three, and Rivers three. Anyone could be a victim of suicide if the situation is not properly managed.

Suicide rate in the world today is at an alarming rate as a result of depression, anxiety and substance abuse, especially when unaddressed. According to the centers for disease control and prevention report of (2023), over forty nine thousand people died by suicide in 2023 while suicide rate increased to 37% between 2000 and 2018. Suicide feelings can affect anyone, of any age, gender or background, at any time. It is occasioned and triggered by feeling of increasingly hopelessness, helplessness and worthlessness experienced by individuals.

People continue to jump off the Lagos Third Mainland Bridge into the Lagoon or ingest ‘sniper’ a disinfectant and all-purpose cleaner turned into a popular and easily available poison, to commit suicide.

Suicide in Nigeria has today become social problem that threatens the existence of mankind and affects the society adversely hence it becomes very necessary to subject the suicide incidence in Nigeria to scientific research as well as proffer solution to incidence of suicide in Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Suicide has emerged as a pressing public health and social concern in Nigeria, particularly among youth and university students. Despite its increasing prevalence, the phenomenon is often misunderstood, stigmatized, or reduced to purely psychological or spiritual explanations, leaving its deeper sociological dimensions underexplored. Emile Durkheim, a pioneer in sociological thought, argued that suicide is not merely an individual act but a reflection of broader social forces. His theory classifies suicide into four types namely, egoistic, altruistic, anomic, and fatalistic with each rooted in the degree of social integration and regulation within a society.

In Nigeria, rapid socio- economic changes, rising unemployment, family disintegration, academic pressure, and weakening communal ties have created conditions that mirror Durkheim typologies. Yet, there remains a significant gap in applying his framework to understand and address suicide within Nigerian context. Without a robust sociological lens, efforts to prevent suicide risk overlooking the structural and cultural factors that contribute to its rise. This study therefore seeks to bridge that gap by examining how Durkheim's theory can be contextualized and operationalized within Nigeria unique socio- cultural landscape, offering a more holistic understanding of suicide and proffering more effective prevention strategy.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

What are the causes of suicide in Nigeria?

What is the effect of suicide on the Nigerian society?

What is the relationship between economic hardship, substance abuse and depression and high rate of suicide in Nigeria

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The general objective of the study is to assess high suicidal rate in Nigeria using the Emile Durkhem work on suicide. Specifically, it has the following objectives:

To identify the causes of suicide in Nigeria

To determine the effect of suicide on the Nigerian society

To determine the relationship between economic hardship, substance abuse and depression and the high rate of suicide cases in Nigeria

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study has both theoretical and practical significance, the theoretical significance is that the study will add to the existing body of knowledge in the area of suicide. The findings of this study will be useful in proffering solutions to the alarming and increasing rates of suicide in Nigeria. The practical significance of the study is that the recommendations will help the government as well as the policy makers to know what suicidal people really need which include effective treatment, counselling and assistance not punishment as attempting suicide is a criminal offence in Nigeria, under section 327 of the criminal code Act and carries a penalty up to one year imprisonment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section of this research work reviewed some empirical literature, theoretical literature, relevant theories and presented theoretical framework for the study.

REVIEW OF EMPIRICAL LITERATURE

Several studies have been conducted on suicide rate in Nigeria. Some of these studies have provoked different reactions from scholars.

In research carried out by the World Health Organisation in the year 2020 in Nigeria, its findings indicated that about 30% of Nigerians that attempted suicide have one form of mental health illusion or the other.

Also, according to 2016 World Happiness Report, it showed that Nigerian had dropped drastically from its 78th position to 103 in the world happiness ranking in 2022, we are now 118th position out of 146 countries, meaning that as the years have gone by, Nigerians have become progressively unhappy, depressed and vulnerable to committing suicide.

Also, according to National Centre for Suicide Research and Prevention (2019) in Sweden, suicide is one of the most common single causes of death. With a population of 10 million people, approximately 1,500 individuals die by suicide every year.

Based on the World Health Organization (WHO) report of (2022), suicide is the fourth leading cause of death in people aged 15 to 19 years. It also stated that over 700,000 people die due to suicide annually.

REVIEW OF THEORETICAL LITERATURE

Having reviewed some empirical literature, it would be appropriate to review some theoretical literature on suicide rate in Nigeria.

EMILE DURKHEIMS THEORY OF SUICIDE

Emile Durkheim seminal work on suicide (1897) laid the foundation for sociological inquiry into suicide, arguing that it is not merely a personal act but a reflection of social forces. He identified three types of suicide based on levels of social integration and regulation:

Egoistic typology occurred as a result of low integration people commit suicide when there are not sufficiently integrated into a social group, Altruistic is due to excessive integration, while anomic suicide can be linked to low regulation, normlessness or social disorganization.

Relating this theory to Nigeria context, it can be said that Nigeria socio-cultural complexity and economic volatility make it a pertinent case for applying Durkheim framework

MENTAL ILLNESS AND RISING CASES OF SUICIDE IN NIGERIA

There is a strong correlation between mental disorders and suicide in Nigeria. Timely diagnoses and treatment of mental illness will help to ameliorate the high rate of suicide cases by mental illness in Nigeria.

ECONOMIC HARDSHIP, FINANCIAL CHALLENGE AND DEPRESSION AND HIGH RATE OF SUICIDE IN NIGERIA

The strongest link to suicide is depression. Depression can be so overwhelming that ending one's life looks like the only viable option.

Also, economic hardship leading to people owing a huge amount of money, frustration, can trigger high rate of suicide. Also, life events can also trigger suicidal thoughts and actions. For instance, losing one's job, long-standing unemployment, divorce or heartbreak in one's relationship, loss of a loved one and may eventually lead to suicide.

SOCIAL FACTORS AND SUICIDE

Social factors can be responsible for the ugly development such as losing social support. According to Emile Durkheim, there are four cardinal social drivers of suicide which are egoistic, altruistic, anomic and fatalistic. For example, among students, egoistic suicide and anomic suicide are more rampant. This can be rightly defined in the context of students losing

social support and having no hope from any social network especially in Nigeria where anomic (lawlessness) now prevails.

According to Durkheim, a renowned sociologist, suicide can be as a result of not only of psychological or emotional factors but of social factors as well. He reasoned that social integration in particular is a factor. The more socially integrated a person is, that is the more he or she is connected to society. Possessing a feeling of general belonging and a sense that life makes sense within the social context, the less likely he or she is to commit suicide. As social integration decreases people are more likely to commit suicide.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK OF SUICIDE

Scholars have advanced several theories in the social science and sociology in particular, that can be used to analyze and explain the concept of suicide. Some of the theories that are relevant to the study will be looked into and adopted as a frame work.

Emile Durkheim's theory on suicide will form the theoretical frame work of this paper. Durkheim is best remembered for his contribution to scientific sociology. His book on suicide (1897) was a major quantitative study in sociology. He emphasized that suicide in every society can be understood in terms of the degree of social solidarity. Durkheim identified three types of suicide-egoistic, altruistic and anomic.

Egoistic suicide occurred when people are not sufficiently integrated to a social group. The social cause for this type of suicide is "egoism" – in ordinate concern for self. Childlessness women, protestant, and others who are excessively individualistic are prone to this type of suicide according to Durkheim.

Altruistic suicide on the other hand, occurs when the individual is strongly attached to society. This type of suicide rests on the existence of a strong "collective conscience" in which individuals choose to die for the survival or interests of the group. Durkheim would include the Palestine and Iraq (Middle East) and Boko Haram suicide bombers in this type of suicide.

Anomic suicide occurs as a result of financial constraints and marital conflicts. Durkheim concluded by recommending professional association in particular and in general, the family, political and religious organizations for the reintegration of the individual into the collectivity.

METHODOLOGY AND MATERIALS

This study adopts a qualitative research design, focusing on the interpretative analysis of social phenomena through the lens of Emile Durkheim's theory, particularly his concepts of social facts, collective conscience and anomie as they apply to Nigerian society. 20 respondents were interview through purposive sampling. These included five university sociology lecturers, five religious leaders (Christian and Muslim), five community leaders (Urban and rural), five youth representatives. Each interview lasted approximately 30 – 45 minutes and followed a flexible guide that explored:

- i. Awareness of Durkheim's concepts of suicide
- ii. Perceptions of social cohesion and moral regulation in Nigeria
- iii. Observations of religious and educational institution as agent of social integration.

In addition, the paper searched, collected and analyzed published new reports about suicide from ten English newspapers in Nigeria. A total of three hundred and fifty (350). Suicide reports

were assessed between January 2015 and December 2023. These were screened and sorted out to further assess high rate of suicide in Nigeria.

RESULTS AND FINDINGS

Suicide is a global phenomenon having a deep consequence not just to the dying person but also towards the bereaved, the community and society. Nigeria with a population of over 200 million is one of the epicenters of suicide in the world with a suicide estimate of 17.3 per 100,000 which is higher than the global (10.5 per 100,000). This high rate of suicide is attributed to depression occasioned by the high rate of poverty in the country. From the findings of the people interviewed, all the respondents agreed that Nigeria's pluralistic society has fragmented moral consensus. 12 respondents, especially youth and lecturers linked suicide rates to social instability, economic hardship, and moral disorientation. This aligns with anomic suicide. Community leaders and religious leaders observed that urbanization and digital life have weakened communal bonds. This reflects egoistic suicide, where individuals lack strong social ties or feel isolated from collective life. Some respondents noted cases of suicide linked to extreme religious expectations or family honour, especially in rural areas. These may reflect altruistic suicide where individuals sacrifice themselves for perceived group values. Also, lecturers and youths interviewed emphasize the lack of mental health education and support systems. This contributes to both anomic and egoistic suicide, as individuals struggle without societal or institutional guidance. Also, three hundred and fifty (350). Suicide reports were assessed between January 2015 and December 2023. These were screened and sorted out to further assess high rate of suicide in Nigeria. It is adduced: that the mean age of the reported cases of suicide was 36.33 (15.48) years

The majority of the reported cases were males (80.6%), married (51.8%), students (33.6%), living in a semi-urban area (40.3%) and among the age group of 25 – 34 (25.3%).

Also, based on the types of suicide committed, a suicide by hanging stood at (48.6%) and poisoning i.e snipers (32.2%). Others like jumping into lagoon etc is 19.2%.

All said and done, in spite of efforts by the Nigerian government to curb inflation, poverty, depression and insecurity in the country, there is the need to alleviate the suffering of the masses so as to reduce drastically the escalating rate of suicide among the populace.

Issues like financial constraints occasioned by the current economic hardship as a result of fuel subsidy removal, high rate of dollar to Naira exchange rate, low minimum wage to workers, etc. is assumed to be precepting factors of suicide in Nigeria.

Also, material conflicts, jilting by lovers, abandonment by spouse etc. also contributed to the high rate of suicide especially egoistic suicide. Comparing the demographic profile with the methods of suicide, it was observed that hanging and poisoning methods of suicide were prevalent across most of the variables. Hanging, in particular was found to be predominant among males, married and separated people, people living in rural, semi-urban and urban areas.

In addition, the known factors including financial constraint, depression and others were by hanging, and the majority of completed suicide by hanging were done at home, while the high percentage of completed suicide by poisoning and jumping into lagoon was caused by material and relationship discord and familiar disharmony.

The findings from research work opined that high suicide rates are caused by the following factors:

Mental health illness: About 30% of Nigerian that attempted suicide has one form of mental health illness or the other (WHO Report 2020).

Economic Hardship, financial challenge and depression: The strongest link to suicide is depression and economic hardship leading to people owing a huge amount of money.

Social factors such as losing social support can be responsible for the ugly incidence of suicide. This can be rightly defined in the context of students losing social support and having no hope.

Marital and relationship discord and familiar disharmony.

The findings, also gave the following effects of suicide on Nigerian society:

It leaves the family of the victim in poverty, especially if the person is the breadwinner of the family and also the family of the person that commit suicide feel isolated. A good example is the woman in the viral 'Mummy Calm Down' video who just committed suicide in Benin leaving 3 children for her husband.

Loss of skilled manpower to the nation as a result of high suicide rate.

It also erode trust and solidarity, key elements of Durkheim's social cohesion

CONCLUSION

This study suggests that suicide being a global phenomenon is having a deep consequence not just to the dying persons but also towards the bereaved, the community and the society. Despite being preventable, many people die by suicide.

The study suggests that the married, depressed, living in semi-urban areas and those deprived of basic needs as a result of harsh economic conditions are prone to committing suicide. It also concluded by advising the government to alleviate the sufferings of the masses so as to make people happy in order for them not to attempt committing suicide.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Timely diagnosis and treatments of mental illness will help to ameliorate the high rate of suicide caused by mental illness in Nigeria. This could be achieved when there is easy access to mental health practitioner for interventions and support for help-seeking suicidal person.

Government should expunge from the criminal and penal codes; laws criminalizing attempted suicides and adopt alternative interventions for suicide attempts like early screening and limiting access to items used to commit suicide. The World Health Organisation Comprehensive mental health action plan 2013 to 2030 recommends that the decriminalization of suicide and suicide attempts is a critical step that governments can take in their efforts to prevent suicide.

Inflation rate should also be reduced by the government. According to National Bureau of Statistics, 2023, inflation rate in Nigeria soared from 28.20% in 2023 to 28.92% in December, 2023. The removal of fuel subsidy by the government led to an immediate increase in the pump price of fuel and a consequent rise in the prices of goods and services. This has led to dwindling of the purchasing power of millions of Nigerians. In December, 2023, the federal government made effort to cut down transportation costs for the populace and introduced many palliatives measures to make life bearable for the masses, but more needs to be done by the government especially in the areas of implementation and distribution.

On their parts, Faith-Based Organizations and civil society groups as change agents should develop the peoples' capacity to welcome new ideas, reject unwholesome behaviours that can endanger individuals' lives and that of the entire society.

Lastly, learning to forgive yourself and others, paying attention to people around you, engaging in family re-orientation such as the promotion of our cultural values sharing of a problem with people that can help out, seeking medical help after trauma, people should be contented with what they have and must try as much as possible to live a stress-free life. All these will help to reduce at an alarming rate the high rate of suicide in Nigeria.

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